

Prioritising EU Environmental Action: The Human Pressure Index as a Spatial Decision-Support Tool

From fragmented data to targeted environmental action

Highlights

- The Human Pressure Index (HPI) integrates land-use, pollution and invasive species into a standardised EU-wide map at 1 km² resolution.
- It identifies where cumulative pressures are highest and where interventions are most urgent.
- Deploying the HPI alongside ecosystem condition indicators strengthens policy coherence and accountability.
- Delivering 2027 and 2030 environmental targets requires spatially targeted actions.
- A large share of EU protected habitats remains in poor condition (81%) [1].

Policy context

The EU's ambitious environmental objectives, from the Nature Restoration Regulation to the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, require targeted, evidence-based and spatially explicit action. Yet policymakers face two structural challenges:

- **Fragmented data on environmental pressures:** Monitoring remains sector-specific (e.g., agriculture, urbanisation, pollution), limiting comparability and coherence across EU Member States.
- **Limited spatial integration:** Without a harmonised EU-wide framework, prioritising where restoration and pollution reduction will be most effective remains difficult.

As a result, restoration funding may not always be optimally targeted, potentially slowing progress towards 2030 objectives.

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What is the Human Pressure Index (HPI)?

The HPI provides a harmonised and spatially explicit representation of anthropogenic pressures, complementing ecosystem condition monitoring within an integrated pressure–condition framework (Fig. 1).

Definition: The HPI is a **spatially explicit composite index** (1 km² resolution) that synthesises 16 harmonised indicators on anthropogenic pressures (e.g., land-use intensity, chemical pollution, invasive species, imperviousness) to identify where ecosystems are most at risk [2].

Figure 1: Pressures vs. Ecosystem Condition. The HPI focuses on anthropogenic pressures on ecosystems, while ecosystem condition measures states of nature. This separation ensures policies address root causes (e.g., land-use intensity, pollution) rather than just symptoms (e.g., biodiversity loss), leading to more effective and sustainable interventions.

KEY FEATURES

- SEEA-EA compatible:** Aligned with the *System of Environmental-Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA)*, the HPI framework organises pressure indicators according to a typology that distinguishes abiotic, biotic and landscape pressure characteristics, ensuring consistency with ecosystem condition assessments and a clear separation between pressures and ecological condition.
- IPBES-aligned:** Structured according to the three major drivers of biodiversity loss identified by the *Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)* – land-use change, pollution and invasive alien species – reinforcing scientific credibility and policy relevance.
- Modular design:** Pressure domains can be weighted differently for ecosystem-specific assessments (e.g., prioritising pollution for aquatic systems, fragmentation for terrestrial habitats).
- EU-wide consistency:** Integrates harmonised datasets from Copernicus, the EEA, the JRC and national monitoring programmes, ensuring comparability across ecosystems and Member States.
- Policy-ready:** Designed for integration into existing EU monitoring, reporting and spatial planning frameworks.

Policy applications of the HPI

Many EU environmental policies require identifying where human pressures undermine environmental objectives. By translating fragmented pressure data into an integrated spatial index, the HPI provides a common pressure layer that enhances coherence, comparability and accountability across EU Member States and directly supports policy implementation (Box 1).

Box 1. How the Human Pressure Index supports key EU environmental policies.

Policy	HPI Application	Example
Nature Restoration Regulation	Identifies high-pressure zones where restoration efforts will be most effective.	Wetlands: Target pressures (agricultural pollution, imperviousness, water exploitation) to restore biodiversity and hydrological functions.
Biodiversity Strategy 2030	Prioritises conservation investments in areas exposed to high cumulative pressures.	Natura 2000 network: Identify sites under high external pressure to prioritise mitigation measures alongside site-based conservation.
Zero Pollution Action Plan EU Soil Strategy for 2030	Maps pollution hotspots (e.g., heavy metals, pesticides, nutrients) to guide regulatory actions.	Drinking water catchments: Identify catchments where cumulative pressures increase risks to groundwater and surface water used for drinking water supply.
Common Agricultural Policy	Highlights agricultural pressure hotspots affecting soil health and biodiversity.	Farmlands: HPI merges pressures to inform CAP greening measures and agroecological transitions.
Water Framework Directive	Evaluates terrestrial land-use and pollution pressures on water bodies to support river basin management.	Rhine Basin: HPI identifies pollution hotspots to prioritise critical runoff areas for water quality improvement.
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Maps cumulative human pressures affecting coastal and shelf ecosystems.	Baltic Sea basin: Synthesises pollution runoff (agriculture, industry, urban) to prioritise coordinated mitigation actions.
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA)	Provides harmonised baselines ensuring cumulative pressures are considered.	Infrastructure projects: HPI provides a pre-project pressure map to assess added impacts of new developments.
SEEA-Ecosystem Accounting	Provides a standardised pressure accounting, complementing condition assessment.	EU-wide accounting: HPI enables consistent reporting of human pressures across ecosystems and Member States.

Policy recommendations

Primary recommendation

Adopt the Human Pressure Index (HPI) as the EU's standardised spatial pressure layer and deploy it alongside harmonised ecosystem condition indicators (see SELINA report D3.2 Policy Brief 2 [5]). Together, these tools establish an integrated pressure–condition framework that allows policymakers both to identify where human pressures are highest and to assess whether policy interventions effectively lead to ecosystem recovery.

Supporting actions

1 Pilot the Human Pressure Index

- Initiate pilot implementation of the HPI in 3–5 representative regions, leveraging existing EU instruments, including the LIFE programme and Horizon Europe, as a first step towards EU-wide deployment by 2030.

2 Integrate HPI into EU monitoring and accounting frameworks

- Incorporate HPI as a standard pressure layer in Natura 2000 reporting, SEEA-EA accounts, and Environmental Impact Assessments by 2027, ensuring harmonised pressure assessment across Member States.

3 Use HPI outputs for prioritisation and evaluation

Apply the HPI to guide:

- Restoration funding allocation,
- Pressure reduction strategies,
- Spatial planning and green infrastructure investments.

4 Establish iterative governance for pressure and condition indicators

- Mandate a technical coordination mechanism (e.g., via the European Environment Agency) to update the HPI and associated indicators, integrate new data sources, and ensure continued alignment with evolving EU policy needs.

References

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